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Research

The impact of Facebook Advertising and Electronic Word-Of Mouth (e-WOM) on Women's purchasing decision process towards cosmetics in Dar es salaam, Tanzania.

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Abstract: *In today's marketing sphere, social media uprising has transformed the communication setting as well as impacted the marketing communication considerably thus the study sought to assess the impact of Facebook advertising and e-WOM on women's purchasing decision process towards cosmetics. This research is a quantitative research associated with multiple regression analysis technique. The respondents of this research are women in Dar es salaam City, Tanzania. This research found that Facebook advertising have an impact on consumer purchase decision process towards cosmetics products as well as e-WOM have significant influence on consumers' purchase decision process towards cosmetics products. Based on the multiple regression model, the coefficient regression value for e-WOM is the biggest with a value 0.939 or 93.9% this demonstrates that e-WOM has a dominant impact on purchase decision process. The study suggests that the cosmetic suppliers need to invest greatly in their Facebook advertising strategy as well as working on the customers feedbacks.*

Keywords: Facebook advertising, e-WOM, Purchase decision process

Introduction

A new era development has enabled human beings to engage with each other in a virtual environment and has absolutely changed the usage of web services. It got here in conjunction with social media as an evolution based on the web 2. Social media is a hybrid element of the promotion mix because in a traditional sense it enables companies to talk to their customers, while in a nontraditional sense it enables customers to talk directly to one another. The content, timing, and frequency of the social media-based conversations occurring between consumers are outside managers' direct control. (Ertemel & Ammoura, 2016)

Social media is not only used to seize up with individuals to have interaction chat with friends and family anymore. Within the past few years, it became a place where individuals, government and companies can engage with each other. The growth of social media has not only changed the acquisition decision technique of clients itself but, also it has completely changed the buying pattern, for instance it has empowered the word of mouth with the aid of becoming an area in which customers can make tips and evaluate the goods. This stands in contrast to the traditional integrated marketing communications paradigm whereby a high degree of control is present (Mangold & Faulds, 2009).

Facebook recently took first place for the most viewed site; thus, it is an everyday occurrence for users to log into Facebook. Facebook is the way to stay connected 24/7 with the ability to log on through computers, laptops, iPads and mobile devices, and is considered by many businesses as a cost-effective strategy to employ when communicating with consumers.

Nevertheless, investigations carried regarding the platforms and how it is alleged by its users still remains scanty. Tuten, (2008) writes that the platform has provided advertisers more strategic advantages, including targeted display ads and sponsored stories called Social Ads, branded profiles which are called Facebook Pages, a developer incentive plan to promote content development known as Facebook Developers, and News feed. Furthermore, the Ads target specific users according to individual profiles and traits in the network.

Many researchers have cautioned that clients' engagement via social media is becoming critical as more entrepreneurs have adopted social media. The study undertaken by Ryan et al, (2017) proves that customers trust other peoples' opinion once they transcribe on social media. The customers' behaviors are not best stimulated with the aid of buddies and circle of relatives anymore, but by means of reviews on social media. Therefore, it's an opportunity for companies to create brand visibility and make their customers become emblem promoters.

By the enhancements in web-based shops the significance of electronic word-of-mouth has extremely increased. When customers get recommendations from their closest or colleagues on social media, they are able to instantly go to the websites which provide the product or service. If the person thinks about the suggestions given by someone he or she knows, the visit to the website can end with purchase (Evans & Erkan, 2014).

Beauty is a physical form that grants social acceptance as well as personal satisfaction. Craig, (2002) explained the enigma of attractiveness, and show how women are, from a tender age, taught to prize relationships with men, whom, they apparently attract with their beauty. Thus, a woman's personal happiness or unhappiness is brought about by her beauty or lack of it and is indoctrinated in women at a very early age. It can be argued that beauty is a currency in every society.

In fact, in most cultures, personal beauty is arguably the most important quality a woman can possess. For these reasons, most marketers in the beauty industry make it an obligation to formulate a powerful social media system so as to uphold a tough position in the client's mind and to gain additional advantages by being available in several kinds of social platforms. Social media such as Facebook stands as a device that enables individuals to oversee and rate various contents as well as brazenly declare what they think and what they trust in.

Since social media has become a part of our daily lives by facilitating some of information without any spatial and temporal barrier. Availability of free information at the right time adds to the charm of social media, thus individuals everywhere in the globe is connected within social media sites such as Facebook to stay informed of latest developments and to attach with friends, share, and validate thoughts so as to make decisions overtime.

By ensuing a description of the context of the above studies, the objectives of this study are as follows; firstly, to identify the influence of Facebook advertising and e-WOM (Electronic Word of Mouth) towards consumers' purchase decision process of cosmetics products. Secondly, to identify the influence Facebook advertising towards consumers' purchase decision process of cosmetics products. thirdly, to identify the influence e-WOM (Electronic Word of Mouth) of communities' members towards consumers' purchase decision process of cosmetics products.

Literature review

Facebook Advertising

On the average, a profile owner on Facebook has about 130 friends together with about 80-page likes. 56% of consumer expressing a greater likelihood of sharing or recommending a

brand after clicking 'like' on the band's Facebook page. Facebook users share more than 3.5 billion pieces of content on a weekly basis.

This suspected increase in Facebook advertisements may probably be a way to please or satisfy the prospective shareholders. Also, Facebook users will be able to create advertisement profiles and pages and have them displayed according to the Facebook terms and conditions. Currently Facebook users have access to a new functionality of creating and uploading a cover page for their profiles. Afterwards the cover pages could be used by companies and organizations to advertise their products and services just as they apply the profile picture function to advertise their various brands.

The latest statistics report from Facebook claims that up to 1 billion people are active users and more than half of them visit the site on every other day. Although there exists a growing popularity in the use of other social networking sites, the unique nature of Facebook as a leading social media lies in the intelligence of engaging the social context of users' activity, the pages they visit, the kind of pages they like and what information they forward or click on as well as the pictures they view or post on their profiles (Facebook, 2012).

Electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM)

Word of Mouth (WOM) is a method of verbal exchange that was described in the beginning as a means of sharing opinion and remarks as regards to the goods and services that human beings were transacting (Aslam et al, 2011). Cheung and Lee (2013) said that E-WOM is online client reviews, it includes analyses and commentaries generated and posted via the stop users of products who've spent their money on the product and indeed used it. It is a credible supply of consumer perception and it can be used via agencies to make corrective or development measures on their products and offerings. E-WOM has developed into a wholly new shape of conversation that exploits modern-day technology. The online reviews are very crucial in influencing the customer to shop for the product.

Consumer Purchase Decision Process

Consumer will have a buyer selection system before eventually comes out with buy choice the buyer selection system consists of 5 ranges model: hassle recognition or need reputation, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase selection, and post-buy behavior (Kotler

et al, 2011:58). In this technique of buy selection, customers think about the attributes of various services and products logically and avail the trial to take decision about specific product that could fulfil his need in minimum cost (Hawkins and Mothersbough, 2007).

Previous Research

(Sharma&DeepikaKalra, 2011) completed a study about how much online social influence marketing has been able to influence product purchase decision and whether customer really trust influential sources, the study gives the result that consumer's influence and trust in online social media is on the rise. Branded websites are the most trusted online social media for product recommendation. Also states that consumers continue to trust more on the opinions of other consumers (online) whom they know.

The encouragement of social interactions among consumers on social media such as communities, reviews or recommendations is likely to establish trust among themselves (Hajli, 2014). Hajli (2014) stated that consumers' socialization through its communities on social media is, directly and indirectly, generating social support that influencing trust towards a product or brand. The exchange of information, feedback, and ratings on social media platform overcome the barrier of insecurity and increase the trust of the consumers and consequently lead to the willingness to purchase the product or service.

Kaur (2016) argued that over the last few years, users have spent more time and shared more information, thoughts, and opinions with each other easily over the Internet. e-WOM played a significant role not that, it has an impact on the cocreation value, and because of that it has an impact upon purchasing decision regardless the type of virtual communities' consumers is in (Danieli, 2016; Balakrishnan et al, 2014). e-WOM generates a greater effect on purchase decision compared to advertisements because members of the communities are sharing their knowledge or experiences that others viewed as unbiased and trustworthy information (Balakrishnan et al, 2014; Hodza et al, 2012; Smith, 2014).

Research Model

Based on the indication on the literature review above led to the formation of the following research model.

Figure 1: Research Model

Source: Researcher, 2020

Research Hypothesis

H₁: Facebook advertising and e-WOM (Electronic Word of Mouth) have an impact on consumers' purchase decision process towards cosmetics products

H₂: Facebook advertising has an impact on consumer purchase decision process towards cosmetics products.

H₃: e-WOM has influence on consumers' purchase decision process towards cosmetics products.

Methodology

Population and Sample

The population in the research was the women who purchase cosmetics through Facebook. The sample in this research is consisting of 100 respondents. The purposive sampling technique was applied in this research where by the following criteria were applied; they should be users of Facebook, women aged above 18 years since this population is the most active in Facebook in Tanzania and purchasers of cosmetics products through Facebook.

Data Collection Method

The study used primary data collection. Primary data obtained through the questionnaires that were designed according to the objectives of this study. The questionnaires were closed ended, in the form of 5-point Likert scale (agree, strongly agree, neutral, disagree or strongly disagree).

Data analysis method

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity is extent to which a construct measures what it is supposed to measure. An easy measure of validity would be to compare observed measurement with the true measurement (Hair et al, 2007:153). Reliability test is established by testing for both consistency and stability of the answer of questions. Consistency indicates how well the items measuring a concept hang together as a set. Alpha Cronbach is reliable coefficients that can indicate how good items in asset have positive correlation one another (Sekaran, 2006:311).

Multiple Regression Analysis Method

Cooper and Schindler (2001:767) stated that multiple regression analysis is a technique to observed value more than X to estimate or predict corresponding Y value. The equation model of multiple regression analysis which used in this research can formulated as shown below:

$$Y=A+\beta_1X_1+\beta_2X_2+e$$

where by **Y**- Dependent variable (Purchasing decision process)

A- the least-squares estimate of the intercept

X₁- Independent variable (Facebook advertising)

X₂- Independent variable (Electronic word of mouth)

β₁-Coefficient of X₁

β₂-Coefficient of X₂

e- Error (other factors which affect consumer purchasing decision process)

Findings

Validity and Reliability

Validity test is used to know whether the instrument is valid or not. The instrument is valid if the value of Pearson Correlation above 0.3. Value of correlation index for relationship among variable independents (Facebook advertising and Electronic Word-of-Mouth) with variable dependent (Consumer Purchase Decision Process) are greater than 0.3 and below the significant level of 5% (0.05). The Correlation between Facebook advertising (0.618) electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) (0.631), with purchase decision process (0.706) show a positive relationship. Hence, the data is considered as reliable since the value of Cronbach's Alpha is above the minimum value which is 0.6.

Classical Assumption

Normality

Table 1: Normality Test

		Facebook Advertising	e-WOM	Purchase decision process
N		100	100	100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	10.80	10.89	1.7535
	Std. Deviation	2.562	3.321	1.70591
	Absolute	.167	.137	.153
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.106	.108	.122
	Negative	-.167	-.137	-.153
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.674	1.374	1.530
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.007	.046	.018

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

Table above shows the results of the *Normality Test*, in this test the criteria used in the decision making are:

- If the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value < 0.05 , the data distribution is not normal
- If the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value > 0.05 then the data distribution is normal.

The Normality Test results in Table, shows that the significance value in the Asymp sig line for Facebook advertising is 0.007, e-WOM is 0.046 and Purchase decision process is 0.018.

The respective values are greater than 0.05. therefore, it can be stated that the data in the variable is declared to be normally distributed.

Multicollinearity

Table 2: Multicollinearity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	3.680	1.099		3.348	.001		
	FB Advertising	.401	.124	.226	3.241	.002	.616	1.623
	e-WOM	.939	.096	.684	9.831	.000	.616	1.623

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

According to Priyatno (2013), a model is called no multicollinearity if the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value is less than 10, and the Tolerance value is less than 1. In table above, it can be seen that the VIF value of all independent variables is less than 10. In the same table it can also be seen that all independent variables have a Tolerance value of more than 0.6. Consequently, the data on variables do not experience multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity

Figure 2: Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

Based on the scattered plot above, it appears that the spots are diffused and do not form a clear specific pattern so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity.

Multiple Coefficient and Correlation Determination

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.843 ^a	.710	.704	2.478

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

In table above, it is shown the Adjusted Rsquare value of 0.704 so that the value of the Coefficient of Determination (CD) can be calculated which is $0.704 \times 100\% = 70.4\%$ which indicates that the Facebook advertising and e-WOM simultaneously has an impact of 70.4% on the purchase decision process, the remaining 29.6% is influenced by other variables not discussed in this research.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 4: Multiple regression Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.680	1.099		3.348	.001
1 Facebook Ads	.401	.124	.226	3.241	.002
e-WOM	.939	.096	.684	9.831	.000

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

Recall that the Multiple Linear Regression model is used to determine the effect of several independent variables on a dependent variable. The computation was done by using SPSS software. The computerized calculation ensures the accuracy of the analysis. From the result in the table above, the model defines as:

$$Y = 3.680 + 0.401X_1 + 0.939X_2 + e$$

Furthermore, when viewed from each regression coefficient it turns out that the most impacting variable is the e-WOM; this demonstrates that the e-WOM has the most dominant dimension to the purchase decision process.

Previous research conducted by Ryan et al, (2017) proves that customers trust other peoples’ opinion once they transcribe on social media. The customers’ behaviors are not best stimulated with the aid of buddies and circle of relatives anymore, but by means of reviews on social media. Therefore, it’s an opportunity for companies to create brand visibility and make their customers become emblem promoters.

T. Wang et al (2016), found that Social media word of mouth referral influence on purchase decision among customer. Consumer share product related information as referral. People have confidence on the Information shared and posted by others in social network and when making purchase decisions.

The ultimate aim of managers should be to utilize their Facebook marketing strategies to grasp the infinite pool of costumers’ insights. The results demonstrated a pattern of Tanzanian consumers exhibiting more positive behaviors towards the e-WOM when it comes to cosmetics products.

Hypothesis Testing

F-Test

F-Test is any statistical test intended to determine whether the independent variables simultaneously influence the dependent variable. This test is done by comparing the F_{count} with F_{table} . If $F_{count} > F_{table}$ as confidence level of 95% $\alpha=0.05$).

Table 5: F- Test results

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1460.665	2	730.332	118.948	.000 ^b
Residual	595.575	97	6.140		
Total	2056.240	99			

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

From the F-test, by using the significant value of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$), the calculated value of F_{count} is greater than the F_{table} ($118.948 > 2,700$). Since the F_{count} is greater than F_{table} , H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It means that the independent variables significantly affect the dependent variable simultaneously.

T-test

T-Test is any statistical test intended to determine the partial effect of each independent variable (X) to dependent variable (Y).

Table 6: Partial Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.680	1.099		3.348	.001
1 Facebook Ads	.401	.124	.226	3.241	.002
e-WOM	.939	.096	.684	9.831	.000

Source: SPSS output processed by Researcher, 2020

The partial influence of each independent variable is as follow:

Facebook advertising (X_1) to Purchase Decision Process (Y)

T-count of X_1 is 3.241 with the level of significance of 0.000. Since the value of $t_{\text{count}} = 3.241 > t_{\alpha}$ (0.05) = 1.660 meaning that the H_{02} is rejected and H_2 is accepted, so based on the hypothesis criteria proposed above, it can be said that Facebook advertising have an impact on consumer purchase decision process towards cosmetics products.

e-WOM (X_2) to purchase decision process(Y)

T-count of X_2 is 9.831 with the level of significance of 0.000. Since the value of $t_{\text{count}} = 9.831 > t_{\alpha}$ (0.05) = 1.660 that means the H_{03} is rejected and H_3 is accepted, so based on the hypothesis criteria proposed above, it can be said that e-WOM have significant influence on consumers' purchase decision process towards cosmetics products.

Conclusion and recommendations

Without doubt it can be concluded that Facebook advertising and e-WOM in current era influences consumers purchase decision process towards cosmetics products, this means that the female buyers are highly inclined by the Facebook advertisements on cosmetics products since their awareness on diverse cosmetics is improved gradually on the other hand the customers normally notice all that's being said and rated by others despite them knowing the commenters in person. The majority of cosmetics customers rely on the information they obtain through their friends so that they can come to a conclusion about a specific product. Some customers are so willing to share their experience after using a particular product on Facebook, so if their experience is virtuous, they will highly recommend the specific product to their family and friends.

The recommendations proposed include:

- The use of sponsored social media influencers who act on behalf of cosmetic products by testing them and giving positive reviews of the specific cosmetic product.
- Cosmetic suppliers need to know and learn about how advertising on Facebook works so that they can design a more effective marketing strategy.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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